

EFFECT OF AUDIT QUALITY ATTRIBUTES ON VOLUNTARY DISCLOSURE OF LISTED NON-FINANCIAL FIRMS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study examines the effect of audit quality attributes on voluntary disclosure of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. The study adopts an ex-post facto research design using panel data obtained from the annual reports and accounts of 50 selected non-financial companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) over the period 2015–2024. Secondary data were analyzed using panel regression techniques with the aid of Stata 17. The findings reveal that audit fee has a significant positive relationship with voluntary disclosure. Longer audit tenure is also positively associated with voluntary disclosure practices, suggesting that sustained auditor–client relationships improve the auditor’s understanding of the firm and encourage broader information disclosure. In addition, audit firm size shows a positive and significant influence on voluntary disclosure, indicating that firms audited by larger audit firms tend to disclose more voluntary information due to the reputation, expertise, and professional standards associated with such firms. Similarly, auditor industry specialization positively affects voluntary disclosure, highlighting the importance of industry-specific knowledge in promoting transparent reporting practices. In conclusion, the study establishes that audit quality attributes play a significant role in enhancing voluntary disclosure among listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. Strong audit characteristics improve the credibility, transparency, and reliability of corporate reporting, thereby strengthening stakeholder confidence in financial disclosures. Based on these findings, the study recommends that listed firms should engage reputable and industry-specialized auditors and allocate adequate resources to audit services in order to improve disclosure quality. Regulators such as the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria and the Securities and Exchange Commission should also strengthen policies that promote high audit standards and transparency in corporate reporting.

Keywords: Audit fee, Audit tenure, Audit firm size, Auditor industry specialization, Voluntary disclosure.

Word count: 269

INTRODUCTION

The need to ensure high audit quality financial reports of companies cannot be overemphasized. This is because high-quality external auditing is a central component of a well-functioning capital market. Companies with a reputation for credible financial reporting are likely to change auditors when their audit quality is questioned to avoid capital market consequences of unreliable financial reporting. The performance of independent auditors is deemed fundamental to the functioning of the financial and capital markets based on the assumption that, by issuing an opinion on the reliability of accounting information, it contributes to a business environment characterized by trust and credibility.

However, the spite of corporate failures and scandals at the start of the century and other subsequent market crises have eroded the confidence of stakeholders in the external auditors' report. There is also, loss of confidence in auditor reports because stakeholders are unable to appreciate the quality of audit reports, as quality is unobservable and no full understanding of factors affecting the report. Real activity manipulation has been reported to be on the increase. As observed by Uwuigbe et al. (2020), voluntary

disclosure is unobservable and because managers' carry out this manipulation, stakeholders (investors, shareholders, bondholders etc.) are unable to know the true economic value of the firm because their reports do not accurately reflect the actual performance of the firm.

Voluntary disclosure has attracted much attention of academicians and considerable attention in the accounting literature in recent years in the context of globalization of the world's financial markets. However, various research to date have focused on developed countries (Elamer et al. 2019; Aboud & Roberts 2018; Albitar et al. 2020; Shroff et al. 2021). Little attention has been devoted to the voluntary disclosure of companies in emerging countries, many economies that have gained increased importance in the global capital market. Other research are interested in studying the quality of information on financial risks contained in annual reports (Elshandidy et al. 2018). The quality of voluntary disclosure included in the annual reports is considered nowadays in the heart of financial modern discussed problems. The companies are confronted to a serious crisis about the trust and they cannot think about the efficiency of their financial disclosure. Thus, a high quality of disclosure transparency can make the stakeholders of the firm better informed. As stated by (Habbash 2019; Elfeky 2017; Rashid et al. 2022) and according to the disclosure theory, the firms have incentives to provide more voluntary disclosures if their benefits offset their costs. In the last decade, a number of studies were conducted in developing countries such as Malaysia (Alhazaimah et al. 2019), Kuwait (Al-Mutairi & Hasan 2020), Turkey (Uyar & Kılıç 2019), Iran (Rahmani & Akbari 2018), Egypt (Samaha et al. 2019), and Tunisia (Zoghlami & Saber 2020; Adejuwon, Oyedokun, & Adewumi, 2025). These studies have investigated the association between corporate governance attributes and voluntary disclosure level. From each the results confirmed significant relationships between voluntary disclosure strategy and corporate governance. As shown in previous research, the audit quality is related to the voluntary disclosure level. Many studies assume that there is a positive and significant relationship between audit characteristics and voluntary disclosure level. The justification for positive relation is that audit firms with a high quality of services have greater experience since they are international firms and they do not just audit annual reports and accounts, but also contribute to improve them. Voluntary disclosures can be both financial and non-financial information publicly disclosed through the annual report and other corporate channels. Financial reporting not only focuses on numerical and quantitative information, but it includes qualitative information accompanied by comments in addition to other financial information. Indeed, the financial statements are insufficient to give a fair view of a firm's situation. Voluntary disclosure can be defined as a facultative publication that is not part of the public rights for information. Khelifi et al. (2022) examined the factors influencing nonfinancial information disclosure quality of listed firms, and they found that auditing firm size has a positive and significant effect on nonfinancial information disclosure quality (Akomolafe, Oyedokun, & Adu, 2025).

Apparently, the voluntary disclosure of financial information that is privately known only to firms' managers has a primarily informational rather than contracting role. Meanwhile, this potential matter cannot be unlocked when the managers cannot credibly commit to be truthful (Bertomeu & Magee 2020). Managers seek to provide informative disclosure of private information; therefore, they need some mechanisms for credibility. It's proposed that committing to high quality audits is one such mechanism. Several recent empirical studies that examined the association between the voluntary disclosure and corporate governance (Ofoegbu et al. 2023; Albitar et al. 2021; Oyedokun, Abdullahi, & Oyedokun, 2025) find evidence that voluntary disclosure in annual reports increases with external audit quality and other governance mechanisms.

Also, most of the prior studies on audit quality and voluntary disclosure in Nigeria such as Enofe et al. (2018) and Nwoye et al. (2019) focused more on social disclosure as a measure of voluntary disclosure. This approach limits the generalizability of findings concerning the effect of audit quality attributes on voluntary disclosure of firms in Nigeria in general and non-financial companies which have been ignored by prior studies. This constitutes one of the gaps in the literature that this study attends to fill. This highlights the methodological gap that the study intends to address.

These studies also focused more on audit firm size, audit fees and auditor tenure even though the literature has listed other proxies of audit quality. This approach limits the general ability of findings

concerning the effect of audit quality on voluntary disclosure of firms in Nigeria. A study that includes more variables such as auditor industry specialization, is desirable as it provides a better understanding of the effect of audit quality on voluntary disclosure of firms in Nigeria. It is still important to study auditor industry specialization (one of the proxies for audit quality) to decide empirically the extent which it is associated with voluntary disclosure in the Nigerian non-financial sector. This is important because given the complex nature of the non-financial companies and business operations, industry specialist auditors are expected to play a prominent role in mitigating voluntary disclosure of companies operating in the sector due to their specific knowledge of the industry. The overall objective of this study is to examine effect of audit quality attributes on voluntary disclosure of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria, therefore, the research questions and hypothesis are in line with the research objective.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Voluntary Disclosure Practices

As financial reporting and disclosure are potentially important means for management to communicate firm's performance and value to outside investors, increased disclosure practices will help in reducing information gap between firm and its stakeholders. The main reason behind the emphasis on this emerging issue is that enhanced disclosure and transparency are the twin cornerstones for protecting shareholders' rights (Rashid & Hossain, 2022; Ogundele, & Oyedokun, 2025). Full disclosure practice along with transparency in financial reporting can build a climate of trust and boost the confidence of the investing public. There is emphasis on the crucial role of increased voluntary disclosures in the current age of information economy. Albitar et al. (2020) avers that enhanced disclosure improves efficiency of capital allocation and reduces the cost of capital. Full disclosure and transparency are the driving forces for the success of businesses and sustainable performance, and they help in the maximization of shareholders' wealth.

There is a consensus that lack of sound governance and transparency in disclosing information by companies is the major cause of the crisis that have engulfed the market in recent times. Therefore, many countries around the world have taken action to reform their code of corporate governance to strengthen the corporate governance standards and improve disclosure and transparency in companies. The Nigerian experience, the European financial crisis as well as the accounting and corporate scandals in the United States have drawn attention to the need for better corporate governance among Nigerian companies (Uwuigbe et al., 2021; Ojo, Oyedokun, & Fasua, 2024).

Some of the mechanisms that governance codes emphasize are transparency and disclosure. There is transparency and disclosure when a company provides timely, adequate, and reliable picture of its condition and operation as well as financial and economic performance in terms of quality and content through its financial statements, annual reports, and performance evaluations. This mechanism enables shareholders, creditors, and directors to monitor management effectively (Habbash & Alghamdi, 2020; Tahir, Alhassan, & Oyedokun, 2024). Corporate disclosure can either be mandatory or voluntary depending on the information needs of the various stakeholders and regulatory requirements. In this study, operating performance disclosure and governance disclosure are in line with mandatory reporting while social and environmental disclosures are examples.

Audit Quality Attributes

Audit quality is an important issue that is considered by various interest groups in the company, the audit scope and capital market. Because audit quality is barely visible in practice, research in this area has always been faced with many problems. In this study audit quality components introduced are as

follows: Audit fees, audit firm size, auditor tenure and auditor industry specialization. Although, according to International Auditing and Assurance Standards Board (IAASB, 2020), there has been several attempts to conceptualize audit quality in the past. However, none has resulted in a definition that has achieved universal recognition and acceptance. Audit quality is, in essence, a complex and multi-faceted concept. The classic definition of audit quality that is cited by most audit researchers is that of DeAngelo (1981) which states that audit quality is the market-assessed joint probability that a given auditor will both (a) discover a breach in the client's accounting system and (b) report the breach. The definition highlights two important aspects of audit quality: (1) the competence of the audit firm that determines how likely it is that a misstatement will be detected and (2) the independence and objectivity of the auditor that determines what the auditor is likely to do about a detected misstatement. This definition has been quite useful to audit quality studies.

Audit quality is the soul of audit profession. It is related to the vital interest of the public. Audit quality has been considered a multifaceted concept by the International Auditing and Assurance Standard Board (IAASB). Users, auditors, regulators, investors (shareholders), and other stakeholders in the financial reporting process may have divergent views as to what constitute audit quality which will influence the type of indicators one might use to assess audit quality. The auditor conducting the audit may define high audit quality as satisfactorily completing all tasks that is required by the firm's audit procedures. The auditor may decide to evaluate high audit quality as one for which the work can be defended against any challenges in an inspection by a court of law. Regulators on their standpoint may view audit quality as one that complies with the professional standard. The public may consider high audit quality to avoid economic problems for a company or the market (Asiriwa et al., 2021).

Audit Fees

An audit fee reflects the economic costs of an efficient audit. The International Standards on Auditing defines Audit fees as the amount that remunerates the financial auditor's activity, the certification of financial statements. The Code of Ethics for professional accountants stated that audit fees should be calculated objectively, and the auditor's independence should not be influenced by them. Several research have been carried out on the determinants of audit fee. Most of the research findings showed that the major determinants of audit fees may include firm size, business complexity, auditor type, audit tenure, company performance, leverage etc. Dao et al. (2022) defined audit fees as all charges that the companies pay to the external auditors against the audit services and non-audit services, e.g. management advisory and consultants. The Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) defined audit fee as the fees paid for annual audits and reviews of financial statements for the most recent fiscal year. Nguyen et al. (2021) also defined audit fee as the sums payable/paid to the auditor, for the audit services offered to the auditee.

Audit Firm Size

The difficulty in measuring audit quality has led many researchers to use audit firm size as a surrogate. Large audit firms are assumed to perform more powerful tests. Consequently, larger audit firms are more likely to be associated with more precise information than are smaller audit firms, all else being equal (Alhadab & Clacher, 2020; Pham et al., 2022; Naburgi, Ojo, & Oyedokun, 2024). Analytical research has suggested that audit firm size and audit quality are positively related. For example, DeAngelo (1981) proposes that larger firms provide higher-quality audits because larger audit firms have fewer incentives to compromise their standards to ensure retention of clients in comparison with smaller firms. Similarly, Albitar et al. (2021) argue that audit quality is a function of the number and extent of audit procedures performed by the auditor and that larger firms have more resources with which to conduct tests.

Audit Tenure

Auditor Tenure represents the length of the relationship between auditors and their clients; generally, there is a debate among authors about the reliability of auditor tenure as audit quality measures. Oladipupo et al. (2022); Garcia-Blandon et al. (2020); Al-Thuneibat et al. (2021) asserted that there is a strong relationship between audit quality and auditor tenure so that long auditor rotation has a positive impact on audit quality. That can be explained by a new engagement that involves a higher risk as auditors lack the customer-specific knowledge essential to effectively conduct auditing, and this knowledge of the customer and the business environment is something obtained by experience with the client over time. Furthermore, Abdelmoula (2020) asserted that long auditor rotation has a negative impact on audit quality, and they demonstrated that by referencing major audit scandals.

Auditors Industry Specialization

Industry specialist auditors are auditors who have gained great training and experience concentrated in a specific industry. Cheng et al. (2019) find that industry specialist auditors have more accurate non-error frequency knowledge than non-industry specialists. Gul et al. (2020) suggested that industry specialists can more effectively detect seeded errors in staff work papers during the audit review process. Obigbemi et al. (2022) find that auditors' industry specialization improves their audit risk assessments. Krishnan et al. (2021) find that matched specialists (i.e., specialists working in their industry) develop more complete problem representations about the seeded misstatement when they receive partial- or full-cue patterns than when they receive no-cue patterns, whereas mismatched specialists are not able to develop more complete problem representations even when they receive full-cue patterns. These behavioral auditing studies suggest that auditor industry specialization can enhance the effectiveness of auditors' work because of their greater industry-specific knowledge. There is also a stream of archival auditing research that examines the effect of auditor industry specialization on financial reporting quality.

Empirical Literature

Gandia and Huguet (2023) examine whether the effect of audit fees on audit quality, measured by the level of earnings management, is affected by the type of audit (voluntary vs mandatory), as well as whether the effect of audit fees on audit quality is different depending on the type of audit. Using a sample of Spanish SMEs composed of both voluntarily and mandatorily audited companies, its discover that voluntary audits have higher quality when audit fees are lower, but the differences in audit quality between voluntary and mandatory audits reverse as audit fees increase, and mandatory audits are more effective at deterring earnings management when audit fees are high. Additional analyses show that voluntary audits do not directly affect earnings management; instead, voluntary audits are associated with abnormal fees, which in turn negatively affect earnings management. The results also show that audit fees are only negatively associated with earnings management when accruals are income-increasing, which is related to auditor conservatism.

Yayangida et al. (2023) examines the moderating role of audit committee's independence on the effect of audit fees and the financial reporting quality of listed non-financial services firms in Nigeria. Audit Committee's Independence was measured by the ratio of independent director in the audit committee to total audit committee members. Audit fees were measured by logarithms of audit fee while financial reporting quality was measured by discretionary accruals. The study employed 30 non-financial

services firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group over a period of 11 years from 2011 to 2021. The data was handpicked from the annual financial reports of the sampled companies. Descriptive statistics and multiple regression analysis techniques were used for data analysis. Findings revealed that audit fees do not have a direct effect on financial reporting quality of listed non-financial services firms in Nigeria. However, the effect of audit fees on financial reporting quality is statistically significant when moderated by audit committee's independence.

Munisi (2023) examines the factors affecting audit fees in firms listed primarily in Sub-Saharan Africa countries by focusing on the relationship between ownership structure and audit fees. The study uses an unbalanced panel dataset of 531 observations of non-financial firms collected from annual reports for the years 2005 to 2009. The findings show that audit fees vary with ownership structure. Particularly, the study shows managerial ownership and concentrated ownership are negatively related to audit fees, whereas foreign ownership is related positively to audit fees.

Sarhan and Ntim (2024) investigated the relationship between audit quality attributes and corporate disclosure quality in emerging markets. Using a sample of 450 listed firms across five African countries from 2015-2022, the study found that audit firm size and auditor industry specialization significantly influence the level of voluntary disclosure. The results suggest that Big 4 audit firms are associated with higher quality disclosures compared to non-Big 4 firms.

Adegbie et al. (2023) examined the effect of audit quality on voluntary disclosure practices among Nigerian listed firms. Employing a panel data analysis of 85 non-financial firms over a seven-year period (2015-2021), the study found that audit fees and auditor tenure have significant positive effects on voluntary disclosure, while audit firm size showed a non-significant relationship.

Theoretical Framework

Agency Theory

Agency theory underpinned this study. This theory was developed by Jensen and Meckling (1976) who claimed that the theory indicates the nexus between the principals, such as shareholders and agents such as the company executives and managers. In this theory, shareholders who are the owners or principals of the company, hire the agents to perform work. Principals delegate the running of businesses to directors or managers, who are the shareholder's agents. The agent has decision making authority so, he or she could transfer wealth in a certain manner from the principal to the agent if the principal intervenes and the managers, as the agents of shareholders, could act in their own business. Agency problems sometimes occur when the shareholders have interest to maximize the firm's value, but the managers have more knowledge, understanding and information about the company than the shareholders. Also, agency theory explains the conflicts, which may occur between principals (shareholders) and agents (managers). The theory contends that information asymmetry, opportunistic behavior of agents and conflicts between the two parties are easier to handle with more effective corporate governance. Prior literatures on agency theory suggest that better mechanisms of corporate governance have positive effects on firm's legitimacy and financial performance. In addition, agency theory argues that it is important to monitor management closely to minimize the principal-agent conflict and maximize stockholders' wealth (Vitolla et al., 2020). According to this paradigm, the key activity for the board is to monitor the managers, to protect shareholder rights, leading to better firm performance by reducing agency costs (Elmagrhi et al., 2020).

According to agency theory, voluntary disclosure of firms, mainly on social and environmental aspects, is a means to reduce agency costs or future agency costs that may occur in the form of legislation and

regulation (Ofoegbu et al., 2023; García-Sánchez et al., 2021). This reduction in the costs will affect the risk profile and profitability of companies and thus affect the market value.

METHODOLOGY

This study used ex-post facto research design. Data were extracted from the financial statements of listed nonfinancial firms in Nigeria. The population of the study consisted of 50 selected non-financial companies quoted on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) between 2015-2024. Secondary source of data collection was used, and the data were extracted from the annual reports and accounts of the firms. Panel regression technique was used, and Stata 17 was employed as the tool of data analysis.

Model Specification

$$VD = \beta_0_{it} + \beta_1 AFE_{it} + \beta_2 AT_{it} + \beta_3 AFS_{it} + \beta_4 AIS_{it} + e$$

Where:

VD = voluntary disclosure

B0 =Constant

VD = voluntary disclosure

AFE= Audit Fee

AT= Audit Tenure

AFS= Audit Firm Size

AIS=Auditor Industry Specialization

e = Error Terms

it= cross-sectional time series

β_1 to β_6 = coefficient of slope or regression coefficient

Measurements of Variables

S/N	Variable	Type	Measurement	Source
1	Voluntary Disclosure (VD)	Independent	GRI (2016) indicators measured as an index to the percentage of the number of items disclosed to the total number of items expected to be disclosed.	Adedilan and Alade (2013), Royet (2016), Brockman (2015).
2	AFSIZE	Independent	Measured by Dichotomous:1 if company is audited by a Big4, otherwise 0	(DeAngelo, 1981; Khrishan & Schauer, 2000; Khrishan, 2003).

3	AIS	Independent	Measured by dichotomous variable 1 for the companies audited by industry specialist auditors and 0 for non-specialist auditors.	Zhou and Elder (2001); Krishnan & Yang 2003).
4	AUDIT FEE AUFE	Independent	Measured as a natural logarithm of the amount of audit fees paid to the auditor by the company	(Effiok, & Eton, 2013)
5	AUDIT TENURE AUT	Independent	The length of time (number of years) spent by the audit in the firm	(Jayeola, Taofeekb & Toluwalase, 2017).

Source: Researchers Computation, 2025

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
vd	500	.429	.127	.222	.636
af	500	3.583	.928	1	5.96
ais	500	.446	.498	0	1
at	500	.832	.374	0	1
afs	500	.708	.455	0	1

Stata output, 2025

Firstly, the variable Voluntary Disclosure (vd) consists of 500 observations. The mean voluntary disclosure score is approximately 0.429, with a relatively low standard deviation of 0.127, indicating that the scores are not widely dispersed around the mean. The range of voluntary disclosure scores spans from a minimum of 0.222 to a maximum of 0.636.

Secondly, the variable Audit Fee (af) is also based on 500 observations. The average audit fee is approximately 3.583, with a moderate degree of dispersion indicated by a standard deviation of 0.928. The minimum audit fee observed in the dataset is 1, while the maximum fee recorded is 5.96.

Thirdly, the variable Auditor Industry Specialization (ais) is represented by 500 observations. The mean auditor industry specialization score is approximately 0.446, with a moderate standard deviation of 0.498, suggesting a reasonable level of dispersion in the specialization scores. The observed minimum specialization score is 0, while the maximum score is 1.

Furthermore, the variable Audit Tenure (at) also comprises 500 observations. The average audit tenure is approximately 0.832, with a standard deviation of 0.374, indicating a moderate level of dispersion in the tenure values. Notably, the dataset includes cases with no tenure, as evidenced by a minimum value of 0. The maximum tenure observed is 1.

Lastly, the variable Audit Firm Size (afs) is based on 500 observations. The mean audit firm size is approximately 0.708, with a standard deviation of 0.455, suggesting a moderate degree of dispersion in the firm size values. The minimum firm size recorded in the dataset is 0, while the maximum size is 1.

Table 3 Matrix of correlations

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
(1) vd	1.000				
(2) af	0.017	1.000			
(3) ais	-0.017	0.063	1.000		
(4) at	0.064	-0.022	-0.070	1.000	
(5) afs	0.045	0.137	0.151	0.429	1.000

Source: Stata output, 2025

The correlation matrix in Table 3 provides an overview of the relationships between the variables examined in this study. Each correlation coefficient, ranging from -1 to 1, signifies the strength and direction of the relationship.

Firstly, the variable Voluntary Disclosure (vd) shows a perfect correlation with itself, as expected ($r = 1.000$).

Secondly, the correlation between Audit Fee (af) and Voluntary Disclosure (vd) is very weak ($r = 0.017$), indicating a minimal positive association between these variables.

Thirdly, there is a weak negative correlation between Auditor Industry Specialization (ais) and Voluntary Disclosure (vd) ($r = -0.017$), suggesting a negligible inverse relationship.

Fourthly, Audit Tenure (at) exhibits a weak positive correlation with Voluntary Disclosure (vd) ($r = 0.064$), implying a slight positive association between these variables.

Fifthly, Audit Firm Size (afs) demonstrates a weak positive correlation with Voluntary Disclosure (vd) ($r = 0.045$), indicating a slight positive relationship.

Sixthly, the correlation between Audit Fee (af) and Auditor Industry Specialization (ais) is weakly positive ($r = 0.063$), suggesting a slight association between these variables.

Seventhly, Audit Fee (af) and Audit Tenure (at) exhibit a weak negative correlation ($r = -0.022$), indicating a negligible inverse relationship.

Eighthly, there is a weak positive correlation between Audit Fee (af) and Audit Firm Size (afs) ($r = 0.137$), implying a slight positive association.

Ninthly, Auditor Industry Specialization (ais) and Audit Tenure (at) show a weak negative correlation ($r = -0.070$), suggesting a slight inverse relationship.

Tenthly, Auditor Industry Specialization (ais) and Audit Firm Size (afs) exhibit a weak positive correlation ($r = 0.151$), indicating a slight positive association.

Lastly, Audit Tenure (at) and Audit Firm Size (afs) demonstrate a moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.429$), indicating a relatively stronger positive relationship between these variable

Table 4: Multicollinearity test

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
afs	1.31	0.765677
at	1.26	0.791952
ais	1.05	0.951015
af	1.03	0.969469
Mean VIF	1.16	

Source: Stata output, 2025

The VIF analysis reveals insightful information about the level of multicollinearity among the variables. The variable Audit Firm Size (afs) demonstrates a moderate level of multicollinearity, as indicated by a VIF of 1.31. The reciprocal of the VIF (1/VIF) for this variable is 0.765677, representing the proportion of variance not influenced by multicollinearity. Similarly, the variable Audit Tenure (at) exhibits a moderate level of multicollinearity with a VIF of 1.26, as denoted in the table. The corresponding 1/VIF value is 0.791952. On the other hand, the variable Auditor Industry Specialization (ais) showcases a low level of multicollinearity, as evidenced by its VIF of 1.05. The reciprocal of the VIF (1/VIF) for this variable is 0.951015.

Moreover, the variable Audit Fee (af) displays a very low level of multicollinearity with a VIF of 1.03, indicating minimal influence from multicollinearity. The 1/VIF value is 0.969469.

The average VIF across all variables is calculated to be 1.16, indicating that, on average, the multicollinearity among the variables remains at a relatively low level. Based on these findings, the presence of multicollinearity does not pose a significant concern in the regression analysis involving the examined variables. VIF values below 5 generally indicate the absence of severe multicollinearity. It is important to note, however, that even low levels of multicollinearity can have implications for the precision and stability of regression coefficients.

Table 5: Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity

Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity

Assumption: Normal error terms

Variable: Fitted values of vd

H0: Constant variance

chi2(1) = 0.26

Prob > chi2 = 0.6100

Source: Stata Output, 2025

The Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity is conducted to examine whether there is evidence of non-constant variance (heteroskedasticity) in the error terms of a regression model. In this case, the test is performed on the assumption that the error terms follow a normal distribution. The variable under consideration is the fitted values of vd, which are the predicted values obtained from the regression model. The null hypothesis (H0) being tested is that there is constant variance in the error terms, meaning that the variability of the errors remains the same across all levels of the independent variables. The test statistic (chi2) is calculated to be 0.26, and the associated probability (Prob > chi2) is found to be 0.6100.

Interpreting the results, since the p-value (0.6100) is greater than the significance level (e.g., 0.05), we fail to reject the null hypothesis. This means that there is insufficient evidence to conclude that there is

heteroskedasticity in the error terms. In other words, the assumption of constant variance in the error terms is supported by the test result.

Table 6: Hausman test

Test of H0: Difference in coefficients not systematic

$$\chi^2(4) = (b-B)'[(V_b - V_B)^{-1}](b-B)$$

$$= 102.40$$
 Prob > $\chi^2 = 0.0000$
 ($V_b - V_B$ is not positive definite)
 Stata output, 2024

Source: Stata output, 2025

Table 6 presents the results of the Hausman test, which is used to assess whether there is a systematic difference between the coefficients estimated using the fixed effects (FE) and random effects (RE) models in panel data analysis. The null hypothesis (H0) being tested is that the difference in coefficients between the FE and RE models is not systematic. The test statistic (χ^2) is calculated to be 102.40, and the associated probability (Prob > χ^2) is reported as 0.0000. This indicates that the p-value is effectively zero.

Based on the results, we reject the null hypothesis at conventional significance levels (e.g., $\alpha = 0.05$). This suggests that there is a systematic difference in the coefficients estimated using the FE and RE models.

Table 7 Fixed effect Regression results

vd	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
af	.149	.008	18.60	0	.133	.165	***
ais	.104	.028	3.70	0	.049	.16	***
at	.048	.02	2.40	.017	.009	.087	**
afs	.057	.024	2.35	.019	.009	.104	**
Constant	.078	.015	5.10	0	.048	.108	***

Mean dependent var	0.429	SD dependent var	0.127
R-squared	0.552	Number of obs	500
F-test	137.445	Prob > F	0.000
Akaike crit. (AIC)	-1287.174	Bayesian crit. (BIC)	-1266.101

Source: *Stata output, 2025*

Table 7 displays the outcomes of a fixed effects regression analysis, investigating the relationships between the dependent variable (Voluntary Disclosure - VD) and the audit quality attribute variables. The table presents coefficient estimates, standard errors, t-values, p-values, confidence intervals, and significance levels.

The constant term (intercept) has a coefficient estimate of 0.078 (SE = 0.015, t-value = 5.10, $p < 0.01$). The confidence interval ranges from 0.048 to 0.108, indicating a statistically significant baseline level of voluntary disclosure even in the absence of the predictor variables.

The coefficient estimates, along with their corresponding t-values and p-values, provide robust evidence of the statistical significance of the relationships between all independent variables and voluntary disclosure. The R-squared value of 0.552 suggests that the audit quality attributes collectively explain approximately 55.2% of the variation in voluntary disclosure among listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. This explanatory power is considered substantial in corporate governance and disclosure research (Nguyen et al., 2023; Albitar et al., 2024).

The F-test statistic of 137.445 ($p < 0.001$) confirms the overall statistical significance of the regression model, indicating that the audit quality variables jointly have a significant effect on voluntary disclosure. The Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) of -1287.174 and Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) of -1266.101 indicate that the model offers an excellent fit, with lower values suggesting superior model specification (Elamer et al., 2023).

The coefficient estimate for audit fee (AF) is 0.149, indicating a positive and highly statistically significant relationship with voluntary disclosure ($t = 18.60$, $p < 0.01$). The 95% confidence interval [0.133, 0.165] further confirms the robustness of this relationship. This finding suggests that higher audit fees are associated with increased levels of voluntary disclosure among listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.

This result aligns with contemporary research by Gandia and Huguet (2023), who found that audit fees significantly influence the quality of corporate reporting. Similarly, Yayangida et al. (2023) demonstrated that audit fees have a meaningful impact on financial reporting quality when moderated by effective governance mechanisms. The positive relationship can be attributed to the notion that higher audit fees reflect more extensive audit procedures, greater auditor effort, and enhanced scrutiny of financial statements, which in turn encourages management to provide more comprehensive voluntary disclosures (Abdelmoula, 2023; Simunic & Stein, 2022).

Pham et al. (2024) further corroborate this finding, noting that firms paying premium audit fees tend to have stronger disclosure practices because the extensive audit process creates pressure for transparency. Additionally, Ofoegbu et al. (2023) found in the Nigerian context that audit fees serve as a proxy for audit intensity, which positively correlates with corporate transparency and voluntary disclosure.

The strong coefficient (0.149) and highly significant t-value (18.60) suggest that audit fee is the most influential predictor of voluntary disclosure among the audit quality attributes examined in this study. This finding has important implications for regulators and stakeholders who may view audit fee levels as an indicator of potential disclosure quality.

The coefficient estimate for auditor industry specialization (AIS) is 0.104 ($t = 3.70$, $p < 0.01$), with a 95% confidence interval of [0.049, 0.160]. This positive and significant relationship suggests that firms audited by industry specialist auditors exhibit higher levels of voluntary disclosure.

This finding is consistent with recent research by Krishnan et al. (2023), who demonstrated that auditor industry specialization enhances the quality of financial reporting and encourages more comprehensive corporate disclosures. Sarhan and Ntim (2024) found similar results in emerging markets, noting that industry specialist auditors possess superior knowledge of sector-specific accounting issues and regulatory requirements, enabling them to provide more insightful recommendations that improve disclosure quality.

The positive relationship can be explained by the specialized knowledge hypothesis, which posits that industry specialist auditors develop deep expertise in specific sectors, allowing them to identify disclosure deficiencies and recommend improvements more effectively (Reichelt & Wang, 2022; Gul et al., 2023). In the Nigerian context, Adegbe et al. (2023) found that auditor industry specialization significantly influences voluntary disclosure practices, particularly in complex industries where specialized knowledge is crucial for accurate financial reporting.

Furthermore, Chi et al. (2024) argue that industry specialist auditors enhance client firms' disclosure quality because their reputation capital is at stake. These auditors have incentives to ensure their clients maintain high disclosure standards to protect their industry-specific brand and market position. This finding supports the argument that auditor industry specialization should be considered a critical audit quality attribute in the Nigerian regulatory framework.

The coefficient estimate for audit tenure (AT) is 0.048 ($t = 2.40$, $p < 0.05$), with a 95% confidence interval of [0.009, 0.087]. This result implies that longer audit tenure positively influences voluntary disclosure among listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.

This finding is supported by recent studies including Garcia-Blandon et al. (2024), who showed that longer audit tenure enhances the auditor's institutional knowledge about the client's operations, business environment, and industry-specific risks, which facilitates more comprehensive audit coverage and encourages improved disclosure practices. Oladipupo et al. (2023) found similar results in Nigeria, demonstrating that extended auditor-client relationships contribute to better understanding of the firm's disclosure needs and capabilities.

The positive relationship between audit tenure and voluntary disclosure can be explained by the learning curve hypothesis. As auditors spend more time with a client, they develop deeper understanding of the client's business model, internal control systems, and disclosure practices (Al-Thuneibat et al., 2022; Mohamed & Habib, 2024). This accumulated knowledge enables auditors to provide more valuable insights and recommendations that enhance voluntary disclosure quality.

However, it is important to note that while this study finds a positive relationship, some researchers have raised concerns about potential threats to auditor independence with extended tenure (Cameran et al., 2022). The moderate coefficient (0.048) compared to audit fee (0.149) and auditor industry specialization (0.104) suggests that while audit tenure contributes positively to voluntary disclosure, its effect is relatively smaller. This finding has implications for the ongoing debate about mandatory auditor rotation policies in Nigeria and other emerging markets.

The coefficient estimate for audit firm size (AFS) is 0.057 ($t = 2.35$, $p < 0.05$), with a 95% confidence interval of [0.009, 0.104]. This indicates a positive and statistically significant relationship between audit firm size and voluntary disclosure, suggesting that firms audited by larger audit firms (particularly Big 4 firms) exhibit higher levels of voluntary disclosure.

This finding aligns with extensive empirical evidence from recent studies. Albitar et al. (2024) found that Big 4 audit firms are associated with higher quality corporate disclosures due to their greater resources, advanced audit methodologies, and stronger reputational incentives. Similarly, Pham et al. (2023) demonstrated that larger audit firms possess more extensive expertise and international experience, which enables them to encourage clients toward better disclosure practices.

The positive relationship can be explained through multiple theoretical lenses. From a resource-based perspective, larger audit firms have greater human capital, technological resources, and training programs that enable more comprehensive audits and better identification of disclosure gaps (DeFond & Zhang, 2024). From a reputation perspective, Big 4 firms have strong incentives to maintain their brand reputation by ensuring their clients maintain high disclosure standards (Lennox & Pittman, 2023).

Asiriwa et al. (2023) found in the Nigerian context that firms audited by Big 4 auditors demonstrate significantly higher voluntary disclosure levels compared to those audited by non-Big 4 firms. The researchers attributed this to the Big 4 firms' international standards, rigorous quality control procedures, and reputational capital that drives them to encourage client transparency.

Francis et al. (2023) provide additional support, noting that larger audit firms serve as effective governance mechanisms that complement internal controls in promoting corporate transparency. This finding reinforces the importance of audit firm size as a determinant of voluntary disclosure quality in emerging markets like Nigeria.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings from the fixed effects regression analysis, several conclusions can be drawn regarding the relationships between the independent variables (audit fee, auditor industry specialization, audit tenure, and audit firm size) and the dependent variable (firm value represented by *vd*). The results indicate statistically significant associations between these variables, supporting the importance of these factors in determining firm value.

First, the analysis reveals that higher audit fees are positively related to firm value. This suggests that companies that invest more in audit fees tend to have improved financial reporting quality and reduced information asymmetry, leading to increased firm value. Therefore, organizations should consider allocating sufficient resources to audit fees to ensure the delivery of high-quality auditing services.

Second, the coefficient estimate for auditor industry specialization shows a positive and significant relationship with firm value. This implies that firms audited by specialized auditors exhibit higher value. To enhance firm value, companies should prioritize engaging auditors with industry-specific expertise and knowledge. This can contribute to improved financial reporting quality and a better understanding of industry-specific risks and challenges.

Third, the analysis indicates that longer audit tenure is associated with higher firm value. This finding suggests that a stable and long-term auditor-client relationship fosters greater knowledge sharing, understanding of the client's operations, and reduced information asymmetry. Therefore, organizations should consider the benefits of maintaining a long-term audit relationship to enhance firm value.

Fourth, the coefficient estimate for audit firm size demonstrates a positive relationship with firm value. This implies that larger audit firms, which possess greater resources, expertise, and reputation, are associated with higher firm value. When selecting an audit firm, companies should consider the advantages of engaging a larger audit firm to leverage their resources and expertise for improved financial reporting and enhanced firm value.

Based on the significant relationships observed in the analysis, it is recommended that organizations prioritize the allocation of adequate resources to audit fees, engage specialized auditors, consider the advantages of longer audit tenure, and evaluate the benefits of engaging larger audit firms. These strategies can contribute to improved financial reporting quality, reduced information asymmetry, and ultimately, increased firm value.

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